

THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF PERCEPTIVE ABILITIES AIMED AT INCREASING THE SOCIAL ACTIVITY OF STUDENTS IN FUTURE TEACHERS.

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Abstract: We understand pedagogical skill as a set of several personal qualities that a teacher should have. These personal qualities allow to organize professional activity at a high level. Such important qualities include the humaneness of the teacher's work; his professional knowledge; Pedagogical skills and pedagogical techniques can be included.

Key words: Pedagogical skill, professional knowledge, pedagogical ability, humanitarianism, professional knowledge, pedagogical ability.

We understand pedagogical skill as a set of a number of personal qualities that a teacher should have. These personal qualities allow us to organize professional activities at a high level. pedagogical technique can be included.

At this point, it is worth noting the following cases: firstly, pedagogical skill is a self-organizing system in the psyche of a person, and humanistic orientation serves as the main factor of this system; secondly, the ground (basis) of the development of professional skills lies in the professional knowledge that determines the true nature of the teacher's actions, their awareness. Orientation and professional knowledge are considered the "skeleton" of high-level professional activity, which ensures the integrity of the self-organizing system; thirdly, pedagogic abilities are considered to be the leaven that accelerates the formation of skills; fourthly, a pedagogical technique based on knowledge and skills, which serves to connect all means of influence with the goal, and also coordinates the structure of pedagogical activity. Thus, all four components of the pedagogical skills system are interrelated. Their growth is not only dependent on external influence, they also require self-development. Self-development is based on special knowledge and skills. The main condition for success is skills, and the tool is pedagogical technique. Now we will dwell in detail on the four elements of pedagogical skills.

1. Humanity of the teacher. If we consider the conflict of ideas and the struggle for one's position as a drama, the whole activity of the educator consists of dramas. Therefore, the higher the level of skill, the more obvious the conflicts. Because the system proposed by the creative teacher novelty is usually met with opposition from outdated views.

The orientation of each teacher's personality is different, the most important and valuable of them are:

- 1) self-orientation, that is, self-confidence, the presence of the desire to "see in me an educated, demanding, real teacher";
- 2) focus on pedagogical tools;
- 3) orientation to the goal of pedagogical activity - a creative approach to the humanitarian strategy, object and means of activity.

For the teacher, the main direction leading to the goal, i.e., humanization of activity, is more important. But the teacher's professional skills are formed only through the sense of responsibility for the future, conscious diligence, and boundless love for children: "If a teacher can embody love for both his work and children," said L.N. Tolstoy.

The direction of humanitarianism defines certain tasks in his daily work as a higher task. Let's compare two different situations. While leading a tour of the Learning Center Museum, a freshman struggles to explain why he should tell the kids about this particular museum. A skilled master pedagogue can see the harmony of several tasks intended from the trip, that is, to lead to self-awareness, to promote the acquisition of the teaching profession, to show the inner aspects of the teacher's work, and thereby to awaken a sense of infinite respect for the owners of this difficult profession and ultimately help the student to stand on a higher cocoon of social development.

Professional knowledge. The professional direction of a skilled teacher is based on two things - his preoccupation with the subject he teaches and the need to communicate with children. The fundamental basis of pedagogical skills is professional knowledge. The teacher's knowledge is focused on the science on the one hand, and on the students who master it on the other hand. The content of professional knowledge is determined by a good knowledge of the theory and methodology of one's subject, pedagogy and psychology. The uniqueness of professional pedagogical knowledge is its complexity. It requires the teacher to be able to synthesize the studied subjects. The basis of the synthesis is solving pedagogical tasks, analyzing pedagogical situations, choosing means of mutual cooperation. In the process of solving each separate pedagogical task, the pedagogical professional knowledge of the teacher is activated and is manifested as a single system.

Along with the complexity and generalization of professional knowledge, its personal coloring is also important. There is a literature class in the 9th grade. Much has been said about Yusuf Khos Hajib's work "Kutadgu Bilig" and his

translations of the characters in it. Pupils also expressed their opinions. The teacher conducting this conversation never once said the words "I think", "I think...". If the knowledge of science and culture is enriched by the teacher's own interests and ideals, it is accepted as his own position. The skill of the teacher is manifested in the humanization of knowledge, giving it spirit. After all, knowledge should be conveyed not just in the form of information obtained from books, but in the way of one's attitude to the world.

Pedagogical thinking - principles and rules are formed on the basis of professional knowledge of the pedagogue. They are manifested in the behavior and behavior of the teacher. This principle builds rules based on each teacher's experience. But it is possible to understand it and see its laws only through professional knowledge. "Forever put on the blackboard" - this is what is said about the teacher. It should also be taken into account that teacher training and professional qualification is a very complicated process. Because professional knowledge should be formed equally at all levels: methodological (knowing the general philosophical laws of development, educational goals and conditions), theoretical (laws and rules of pedagogy and psychology, basic forms of activity, etc.), methodical (educational - the level of being able to see the educational process), technological (the level of solving practical tasks of education in certain conditions). It requires a certain level of developed professional thinking, that is, the selection, analysis and processing of knowledge aimed at the implementation of a pedagogical goal.

But the acquisition of pedagogical skills is not strictly limited to the level of growth of professional knowledge. Indeed, a student who excels at a university may not succeed in pedagogical practice. Because there are special features of successful activity, stimulators of professional growth - abilities.

Pedagogical skills. So, the third element of the system of pedagogical skills is pedagogical skills. They show the course of mental processes that determine the effectiveness of pedagogical activity. The classification of pedagogical skills is given in several studies.

We have to choose the most important ones that lead to pedagogical skills. Analyzing the scientific research conducted in this regard, we distinguished six main types of abilities.

1. Communicativeness. This ability is determined by the ability to communicate with people, benevolence towards them.
2. Perceptual abilities. It is determined by professional acumen, empathy, pedagogical intuition.

3. Personal balance, i.e. the ability to exert willpower and come to a logical conclusion.
4. Emotional balance, that is, the ability to control oneself.
5. The ability to make optimistic predictions.
6. Creativity.

It is possible to know the pedagogic ability of a future pedagogue depending on the pace of professional training, how deeply and carefully he mastered the forms and methods of pedagogical activity.

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